

Supplementary materials - Per-segment iBLEU evaluation tables

This document complements the conference companion "AI and Renaissance Poetry: How Prompt Language Shapes Literary Translation" (Tenace, 2026) by providing the full per-segment output of the iBLEU evaluation summarised in Table 2 of the main paper.

Reading guide for the tables that follow

The tables below were generated through the iBLEU dashboard, an open-source interface for segment-level BLEU evaluation. The interface employs generic placeholder labels (*fakedoc*, *fakeref*, *fakesys*, *fakesys2*) that map onto the texts under analysis as follows:

iBLEU label	Corresponds to
<i>Source</i>	The original Italian verse by Petrarch (RVF 90)
<i>Reference (fakeref)</i>	Joseph Tusiani's English translation, used as the gold standard
<i>Hypothesis (fakesys)</i>	DeepSeek translation generated through the Italian prompt
<i>Hypothesis (fakesys2)</i>	DeepSeek translation generated through the English prompt
<i>Document (fakedoc)</i>	Internal identifier of the quatrain as a single document unit

Interpreting the numerical values

The number reported in square brackets next to each hypothesis line (e.g. $[0.16]$) is the BLEU score of that translation against the reference, on a 0–1 scale. Higher values indicate greater lexical and phrase-level overlap with the gold standard. The Δ _BLEU value displayed in the segment header is the absolute difference between the two hypothesis scores, expressing the gap between the Italian-prompt and English-prompt outputs at the verse level.

As noted in the main paper, BLEU scores are intrinsically low when applied to poetic translation, due to the wide lexical and structural latitude that the genre permits. The comparative ordering of the two conditions, rather than the absolute magnitude of the scores, is what carries interpretive weight here. The full discussion of these results is provided in section 5 of the main paper.

Configuration details

All scores were computed through the iBLEU dashboard (<https://github.com/desilinguist/ibleu>), using its default smoothing settings. Each verse was evaluated as an independent segment within a single-document corpus, with Tusiani's translation as the only reference text.

ID	Segment 1, Document "fakedoc" [$\Delta_{BLEU}=0.11$]
Source	Erano i capei d'oro a l'aura sparsi
Reference (fakeref)	loose in the breeze , the gold of all her hair
Hypothesis (fakesys)	her golden hair was spread to the breeze , [0.16]
Hypothesis (fakesys2)	her golden hair streamed loose to zephyr's play , [0.05]

ID	Segment 2, Document "fakedoc" [$\Delta_{BLEU}=0.05$]
Source	che 'n mille dolci nodi gli avolgea,
Reference (fakeref)	was in a thousand playful ringlets blown ,
Hypothesis (fakesys)	which in a thousand sweet knots it entwined , [0.11]
Hypothesis (fakesys2)	in countless sweet coils by the breeze entwined , [0.06]

ID	Segment 3, Document "fakedoc" [$\Delta_{BLEU}=0.05$]
Source	e 'l vago lume oltra misura ardeadi que
Reference (fakeref)	and more than ever the great luster shone
Hypothesis (fakesys)	and the radiant light burned beyond measure [0.07]
Hypothesis (fakesys2)	while those bright eyes (now dimmed) with fire combined [0.02]

ID	Segment 4, Document "fakedoc" [$\Delta_{BLEU}=0.05$]
Source	i begli occhi, ch'or ne son sì scarsi;
Reference (fakeref)	of those fair eyes , less ardent now and fair .
Hypothesis (fakesys)	from those beautiful eyes , now so scarce to me ; [0.09]
Hypothesis (fakesys2)	to blaze beyond all measure in their day . [0.04]